

ORIGINAL PAPER

Is homeopathic 'immunotherapy' effective? A double-blind, placebo-controlled trial with the isopathic remedy *Betula* 30c for patients with birch pollen allergy

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The objective of the study was to examine the effect of the homeopathic remedy *Betula* 30c vs placebo for patients with birch pollen allergy. A double-blind, randomized, placebo-controlled trial was carried out. Tablets were given for 4 weeks during the birch pollen season. The setting was Oslo, Norway, May 1995.

Patients were aged between 18 and 50 y; 32 patients received *Betula* 30c tablets and 34 patients received placebo tablets.

The main outcome measure was the total score of 17 different allergy symptoms. Daily total scores were calculated, as well as differences and ratios between the run-in and the following time periods. Point estimates of the median difference between the experimental and placebo groups, with their 95% confidence intervals, were the main measure of effect.

No statistically significant difference between the groups was found during the first and last period of May. However, from 8 to 18 May, a clinically interesting difference was revealed between the groups, those receiving *Betula* 30c having fewer and less serious symptoms. For some days these differences were statistically significant. Surprisingly, this group reported more aggravation from the tablets than did the placebo group.

With a statistical power of 70% for a defined clinically interesting difference (25%), the present results indicate that treatment with *Betula* 30c during the pollen season deserves further attention. *British Homeopathic Journal* (2000) 89, 161-168.

Keywords: *Betula* 30c; birch pollen allergy; hay fever; homeopathy; isopathy

Introduction

The prevalence of allergy is increasing in the Western world, and frequency estimates for hay fever in different countries vary from 1.6% to 24%.¹ Hay fever, or more correctly seasonal allergic rhinitis, is due to pollen from trees, grasses or flowers.² In Scandinavia the most common tree pollen allergy is due to the Silver birch (*Betula alba*). In Southern Norway this tree has its flowering season during May.

Standard treatment includes pharmacologic therapy or allergen-specific immunotherapy.³ Several studies have confirmed the efficacy of immunotherapy, where small amounts of the actual allergen is given orally or injected over years to build up the immunity.⁴⁻⁷

Homeopathic 'immunotherapy' (one kind of so-called isopathy) resembles hyposensitization, the main difference being the degree of dilution of the allergen used.^{8,9} The term isopathy derives from the Greek *isos* meaning 'equal', and isopathic remedies are made from the supposedly causative agents or products of a disease. These remedies are then given to a patient suffering from that same disease. The isopathic method therefore includes the prescription of substances to which a patient is hypersensitive or

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allergic, such as wheat, milk, or a certain type of pollen.¹⁰ The allergens are submitted to the same dilution and succussion procedures (called potentization) as genuine homeopathic remedies used in 'classical homeopathy'.¹¹ The dilution up to and beyond the limit of Avogadro's number (6.02×10^{23}) makes the effect of homeopathic remedies doubtful and controversial, the main argument being that there is no scientific explanation of why an 'infinitesimal dilution' could work.¹²

A recently published meta-analysis of various homeopathic studies suggests, however, that there is a difference between homeopathy and placebo, but the evidence for efficacy in any single condition is insufficient.¹³ Nevertheless, a meta-analysis of the homeopathic treatment of pollinosis with *Galphimia glauca* favoured homeopathy in comparison with placebo.¹⁴ Only two double-blind, placebo-controlled studies which showed statistically significant effects of homeopathic 'immunotherapy' (isopathy) have been published in well-known scientific journals; the first one on hay fever, the second one on allergic asthma.^{15,16} Therefore, there are still major unsolved questions related to the study of both isopathy and classical homeopathy. Especially when it comes to dosage, uncertainty prevails, since both the dilution mechanism and the number of tablets to be administered are controversial.^{11,17,18}

Homeopathic treatment (both isopathy and classical homeopathy) is quite popular in Norway (about 500 000 consultations in 1991 in a population of 4.3 m people)¹⁹ and patients with allergy are often treated with an isopathic remedy. We therefore decided to carry out a study on birch pollen allergy, being one of the most frequent early-season pollen allergies in Norway. In addition, we could recruit patients before they left for summer holiday in June. We studied isopathy with a single substance (potentized birch = *Betula*), with the dilution of the remedy being so high that 'nothing' was left of the original solute (viz. a so-called 30c potency, ie a 10^{60} times dilution). *Betula* 30c was specially made for this purpose and has not earlier been tested in a clinical trial as far as we know.

Isopathy can easily be tested in randomized, controlled trials because the same remedy is given to all the patients (in contrast to the individualized regimen used in classical homeopathy). This makes the analysis of the results more straightforward, and in addition the study may be reproduced by others.

The aim of the study was to see whether isopathy with *Betula* 30c could reduce symptoms of birch pollen allergy significantly better than placebo treatment.

Patients and methods

Our study was administered from the University of Oslo in 1995 as a cooperation between two otorhino-

laryngologists, three classical homeopaths and a general practitioner (S Aabel).

Recruitment and patient selection

Patients were recruited through a newspaper article. They all lived in the Oslo area and were given an initial informative telephone interview by the GP, followed by a clinical interview regarding their allergy and general health. Those who met the inclusion criteria were invited to a preliminary clinical examination by the otorhinolaryngologist. The examination included a skin prick test for allergy to alder, hazel, birch and grass pollen as well as allergy to cat, dog, mite and horse. Inspection of the nasal mucosa was also performed. If the skin prick test was positive for birch (more than 3 mm in diameter after 20 min), and the nasal mucosa appeared normal, the patients were instructed to contact one of three participating homeopaths. The homeopaths performed a classical homeopathic interview and collected data that will be published later. Thereafter, the patients were instructed to contact their homeopath when the allergy started in springtime.

Patients of both sexes, 18–50 y of age, were included and required to have a clear history of birch pollen allergy and a positive skin prick test for birch. Excluded were patients with diseases of any kind other than the above-mentioned allergy (ie also those suffering from eczema and asthma) and conditions causing nasal blockage (like polyps, septum deviation and chronic oedema due to perennial rhinitis). Also excluded were patients using medication of any kind (also contraceptives), women who were pregnant or likely to become pregnant, lactating mothers, and finally people not willing to stop drinking coca cola or coffee during the treatment period. This last requirement was posed because of a possible interference of these drinks with homeopathic treatment.¹¹

When the patients got allergy symptoms or the allergy season started, they scored four nasal symptoms (discharge, stuffiness, itching, sneezing) and the presence of eye symptoms on four-point scales (0 = none to 3 = severe). For inclusion in the study, the combined score had to be at least 3. This is in accordance with other studies on allergy.²⁰

Trial design

The study was designed as a 4 week, double-blind, placebo-controlled trial. Each centre received tablet vials randomly coded with a number, in such a way that half of the patients at each centre would receive placebo and the other half *Betula* 30c. Each patient got two vials, one labelled A and the other labelled B. To establish a baseline of symptoms all patients received placebo tablets (vial A) for 3 days during

the run-in period, blind to the nature of the tablets (the principal investigator was not blind to the run-in treatment). This run-in period started when the patient first experienced allergy symptoms. For some patients this could be as early as the end of March due to pollen from hazel and alder, whose pollen immunologically cross-reacts with birch.² The birch pollen season was defined as 27 April to 28 May (ie start 1 week before there was detectable pollen in the air). Thereafter, from day 4 onwards, the patients were instructed to use vial B containing either *Betula* 30c or placebo. The instruction was: 'One tablet daily until the allergy gets better, then stop. Resume tablet intake if symptoms return. If very high levels of pollen occur, you may take as much as three tablets a day.' The patients had contact with the homeopath three times during the study period: initially, after 2 weeks and finally after 4 weeks of treatment. The patients were instructed to abstain from coffee and coca cola (to avoid caffeine intake) at least 3 weeks before entering the study. They should also as far as possible avoid operations (including dental treatment), vaccination and exposure to camphor, peppermint and menthol, as these factors are believed by homeopaths to interfere with treatment.¹¹ They were allowed to take local antihistamines or steroids (nasal spray and eye drops). If the symptoms were very bad, they could also use systemic antihistamines and antiasthmatics (including steroid inhalers).

Study diaries

The homeopaths instructed the patients how to fill in registration forms for allergic symptoms. All patients were asked to complete a diary for 28 days, scoring 17 different symptoms each evening on a symptom score list from 0 to 3 (nose blockage, nose drip, nose itch, nose sneeze, eye drip, eye itch, eye oedema, interior throat itch, exterior throat itch, throat mucus, palate itch, ear itch, skin itch, skin oedema, skin eczema, asthmatic breath and coughing).

The minimum possible total score each day was 0 and the maximum 51. Various assessment procedures have been used previously; some studies on allergic rhinitis employed a score system like that we chose, with a numerical value,²¹ while others used the visual analogue scale (VAS).^{15,16,22} We decided to evaluate the allergy as a sum score based on a range of different symptoms and not as a 'global' or 'all in all' response (VAS). Then we could sharpen the analysis by determining the impact of single symptoms like eye itch or nose blockage.

Patients were also asked to record the number of experimental tablets taken, as well as the use of rescue medication (conventional anti-allergy treatment), their feeling of general energy level (measured on a scale from 0 = 'no energy' to 3 = 'good energy level'), and the occurrence of acute diseases other than the allergy.

Drug preparation

The medication used in our trial were produced by Drogecentralen Göteborg (DCG), Sweden, according to GMP (Good Manufacturing Practice).²³ The form was sucrose globules, the basis for most homeopathic remedies, impregnated with a succussed and diluted solution. In a clinical trial, these sucrose globules can be used as placebo tablets because they are identical to the verum with respect to colour, size, shape, taste and weight. There is an ongoing discussion whether or not one should impregnate the placebo tablets with the solvent used for the remedy, ie a diluted and succussed solution of water and ethanol.²⁴ Then the only difference between test and placebo would be the addition of the test substance (*Betula*) to one of the liquids before the dilution/succussion procedure. However, for practical reasons, we decided to use plain sucrose globules without impregnation as placebo tablets. The homeopathic tablets were impregnated with a solution of *Betula alba* 30c. This solution was made from a birch pollen extract. To reach a dilution of 30c one starts out with 1 part of extract, mixes it with 99 parts of distilled water and shakes it vigorously by hand (called succussion) 12 times. From this solution (1c) one part is mixed with 99 parts of water, then shaken, giving a 2c dilution, and so forth. Up to 27c water is used as solvent. 28c is made from one part of 27c and 99 parts of 80% ethanol. 29c is processed in the same way, but 30c is made from 1 part of 29c and 99 parts of 95% ethanol. Then the sucrose globules are impregnated in the following way: 9 ml of *Betula* 30c is poured over 750 g of globules in a 1 l bottle. The bottle is placed in a shaking machine for 5 min. The globules are then left to dry in the open bottle at room temperature for 2–3 weeks. All the solution is not fully absorbed into the globules. About 10–20 %v/v is left on the interior wall of the bottle. The impregnation procedure is performed three times. The vials were sent to a statistician for random coding and then distributed to the participating homeopaths.

Statistics

A 5% significance level and statistical power of 90% were chosen. We decided that a five-point difference in total sum score would be the minimum value worthy of detection. Consequently, a power analysis required the admission of 70 patients given an assumed standard deviation of 6. Depending on whether the patients had few (eg 8) or many symptoms (eg 20), this would give clinical differences ranging from 25 to 60%.

The mean daily symptom scores from days 1, 2 and 3 of the run-in period (RI) was calculated for all the subjects, as well as the mean scores for days 5, 6 and 7, a period chosen beforehand to detect any immediate symptomatic improvement due to the test treatment, which started on day 4. This variable was called EP1 (experimental period 1). As main outcome measure

we chose the median daily symptom sumscore in the pollen period for all the subjects, giving rise to point estimates for the differences between the test and placebo groups. A two-sided Wilcoxon–Mann–Whitney two-sample test was used to compare test and placebo groups. Wilcoxon’s sign test for paired comparisons was employed to evaluate the symptom changes in each person from run-in to the first experimental period. All statistical analyses (MINI-TAB computer program; Minitab, State College, PA, USA) were performed before the treatment code was broken.

Ethics

Informed and written consent was obtained from all patients. The study was part of a research programme on alternative and complementary medicine under the Research Council of Norway and was approved by the Regional Ethics Committee for Medical Research and also by the Homoeopathic Ethical Committee.

Results

Patient characteristics, pollen counts, weather

Of 240 people willing to participate, 163 were excluded according to the selection criteria. Seven persons were excluded due to a negative skin test. Seventy were selected to enter the study. One patient dropped out after 7 days of treatment because of travelling abroad. She did not return the form. Three patients initially included were later excluded due to lack of allergy symptoms (Figure 1). Consequently, 66 patients completed the study. The treatment groups were comparable with respect to age, sex, years with allergy, presence of other complaints, and previous experience with complementary medicine (Table 1).

Pollen is regularly counted in the Oslo air during the flowering season, and in 1995 a moderate and variable concentration of birch pollen was measured (Figure 2). Notably, allergic individuals experience symptoms when the pollen count is between 30 and 100 grains per m³ of air.

The peak count of pollen in Oslo on May 5 was 2100 grains per m³ of air (mean for the whole birch pollen season was 404). The mean May temperature was 9.8°C, which one would characterize as a cold May.

Twenty patients developed allergy symptoms and entered the trial before the start of the birch pollen season. This was due to their allergy to alder and hazel. Two of these even finished their 4 week period before the birch pollen season started.

Symptom course

The pollen season started on 2 May, giving the two groups a rise in symptom score as shown in Figure 2, upper panel. From 2 May to 7 May there was no detectable difference in symptom scores between the

Figure 1 Consort flow diagram showing numbers recruited, randomized, excluded, drop-outs and individuals included in the final analysis.

Table 1 Similar baseline characteristics of patients treated with *Betula* 30c or placebo

	<i>Betula</i> 30c	Placebo
Age of patients ^a (y)	34 (19–48)	36 (21–49)
Sex	15 f, 17 m	15 f, 19 m
Duration of allergy ^a (y)	15 (2–32)	12 (2–28)
Other complaints ^{a,b}	4 (0–9)	4 (0–8)
Prior UT ^c	12	14

^aMean values with ranges in parentheses.
^bNumber of present minor complaints other than allergy, like headache, backache, cold feet etc.
^cNumber of patients who had tried unconventional treatment (UT) before this study.

groups. However, the following period from 8 May witnessed an improvement of symptoms in the *Betula* group that lasted for 10 days. In this period the single-day *P*-values range from 0.41 to 0.02, and the 95% confidence intervals for the point estimates of the

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Figure 2 Overview of symptom scores and atmospheric conditions. The upper panel shows symptom course for the two groups in the pollen period, with number of patients participating. The middle panel shows the difference in median symptom score between the two groups, with point estimates and their 95% confidence intervals each day. The two lower panels show mean air temperature and pollen counts in the period from 27 April to 28 May.

differences do not include zero value on three of these days (Figure 2). During the last period of the pollen season the symptom score was still lower in the *Betula* group, but there was no statistically significant difference between groups. On the other hand, of clinical interest is the upper threshold of the confidence interval of the difference during this period, viz. a maximum difference of 5 on 25 May. This means that the trial has not ruled out the possibility that the treatment is worthwhile, but a larger sample size is needed to eliminate a type 2 statistical error.

The difference from the run-in period to the first experimental period (EP1) showed a statistically and clinically significant improvement in the *Betula* group ($P = 0.004$), which was not seen in the placebo group. However, this improvement was not maintained during the next period. This improvement is reflected by the individual score ratios; ie the relationship between Run in values (RI) and experimental period values (EP1, 2, 3). The 95% confidence intervals for these ratios fell below 1.00 during all three periods for the *Betula* group within the birch pollen season, but

only during the first period within the whole tree season (Figure 3). This indicates that the improvement can be maintained throughout the whole period of allergen exposure.

Compliance, aggravation, and use of antihistamines

The forms filled in by the patients indicated that they, contrary to the written instructions, in general had continued to take tablets even if they had experienced a marked improvement of their allergy. In the homeopathic group only 25% of the patients took their medicines as prescribed, the main problem being that they did not stop when they got better.

During the allergy season many patients reported an aggravation of allergy symptoms both immediately and some hours after taking the tablets. Therefore, after the pollen season, but before the code was broken, we sent a questionnaire to all our patients asking them about aggravation of symptoms possibly due to the tablets. The questionnaire contained one statement: 'I felt an immediate worsening of allergy symptoms just after intake of tablets, or if I took too many tablets'. The answer options were yes, no or don't know. A difference was found between the two groups, in that 13 patients in the isopathic group reported worsening of symptoms, possibly due to the tablets, as opposed to only four patients in the placebo group ($P=0.03$, χ^2 test).

The use of rescue medication, like local and systemic antihistamines, is shown in Table 2. The per-

sons in the *Betula* group using rescue medication were those who reported worsening from test tablets. Five of these patients got a quite serious asthmatic reaction which necessitated frequent use of antiasthmatics (Table 2).

The patients' and the homeopaths' opinion about what kind of tablets the patients had received, whether placebo or homeopathic remedy, did not differ appreciably between the groups.

Discussion

An initial rise in symptom score during the pollen season was found in both groups; thereafter there was an improvement in the *Betula* group over the next 10-day period. The difference between the groups was for some days statistically and clinically significant. Moreover, there was an improvement of symptoms in the *Betula* group from each patient's run-in to the first experimental period, which was not seen in the placebo group. Then, for the last 10-day period the *Betula* group increased their symptom scores, thus obliterating any differences vs the placebo group.

Daily symptom score assessment (Figure 2) involves a number of statistical comparisons requiring a re-definition of the level of statistical significance, using the Bonferroni correction, for example. Therefore differences were found that would not have been discovered if we had performed an overall test, comprising the whole experimental period. However, the symptom score differences between the groups were positive (Placebo > *Betula*) in 24 of the 32 days. Furthermore, the improvement in the *Betula* group from the 3-day run-in to the following 3-day experimental period (Figure 3) was indeed suggestive of a real treatment effect.

The statistical power with the number of subjects and changes in symptom scores that we found, was 71%. To obtain a power of 90% we would have needed 50 persons in each group which is more than we intended to include, due to a larger symptom score variance than anticipated.

We used rigorous selection criteria, which gave us a sample of patients that was probably not very typical for the whole population of birch allergic individuals. The participants were all healthy, used no medication, were only suffering from pollen allergy and had volunteered in response to a newspaper announce-

Figure 3 Symptom score ratios for the three successive periods 1: EP1 (day 4-7), 2: EP2 (day 8-14), 3: EP3 (day 15-28) are shown, for the total tree pollen season (panel A). Data are given as medians with their 95% confidence interval and number of patients. The figure illustrates a significant alleviation of symptoms (ratio with 95% CI < 1) in the *Betula* group, in A for the two first periods, in B for all three periods.

Table 2 Use of rescue medication in the two groups, given as number of doses and number of users: some subjects with aggravation symptoms (bronchial asthma) in the *Betula* group

	<i>Betula</i> 30c		Placebo	
	Subjects	Doses	Subjects	Doses
Nasal spray	12	186	20	324
Eye drops	20	342	14	402
Antihistamine tablets	9	80	9	101
Antiasthmatics	6	125	3	43

ment. Moreover, even though the selection was very strict, we did not manage to obtain a sample of people with pure birch pollen allergy, since many of them also reacted to alder and hazel, experiencing allergy symptoms before the birch pollen season. Actually, 20 individuals started with the test medication before the birch season.

In retrospect, our tablet instructions had some obvious weak points. The participants were instructed to take one tablet a day until they got better. We did not define the word 'better', and they were not told how they could find out by themselves precisely what it meant. In addition, they were told to take up to three tablets a day if high concentrations of pollen occurred. They were not told what was meant with 'high concentrations'. The final result was therefore low patient compliance, only 25% in fact taking the tablets correctly, the rest either taking too many tablets when medication was indicated or not stopping when they got better. This could be due to lack of knowledge about and understanding of the philosophy of homeopathy which says: 'If one tablet works, an additional one is not necessary.' Homeopaths even claim that it is possible to develop allergy symptoms from the tablets themselves if overdosed. They call this a 'proving situation', leading to aggravation of symptoms, and this is in fact the way real homeopathic remedies are investigated both today and in the past.^{25,26} The 'aggravation phenomenon' has been described in other studies of homeopathic treatment, both with isopathy^{15,16} and classical homeopathy.²⁷ The patients' report of aggravation might thus suggest an overdosage of the remedy. This would lead to an underestimation of the real relief of symptoms especially during the last period of May. To clarify this, a new study must be performed in which the patients receive more detailed instructions on how to use the tablets.

This is the first evaluation performed with this isopathic birch remedy, and we therefore must be cautious when comparing our results with those of other studies of homeopathic 'immunotherapy'. Our study is in several respects similar to the positive isopathic studies published by Reilly *et al.*^{15,16} Allergic patients were investigated by them, models with a 30c potency of allergens were used, and the main measure of response was reduction of overall symptom intensity in comparison with baseline scores, obtained during a placebo run-in period. However, the tablet instructions differed in that we allowed our patients to medicate themselves throughout the whole period, whereas in Reilly's studies they received a given dose during a given period. Moreover, we used a shorter, 3 day (vs 7 day in the Reilly hayfever study) run-in and chose early symptom relief as one outcome measure, in addition to a day-to-day median symptom score during the pollen season.

In conclusion, even though the present findings are suggestive, there is a need to perform more random-

mized, controlled trials for each single condition or disease, testing out a single homeopathic remedy in each study. Parallel to this kind of clinical experiments one should pay more attention to laboratory research that has been done on high dilutions and examine whether it is possible to reproduce the intriguing results that have been published.²⁸

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